

THE SYMBOL OF WOMEN IN FAY WELDON'S LITERARY WORKS

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Annotation: Fay Weldon CBE was an English author, essayist and playwright, whose work has been associated with feminism. In her fiction, Weldon typically portrayed contemporary women who find themselves trapped in oppressive situations caused by the patriarchal structure of British society. Her works "Weekend" (story), "The fat woman's joke" and others are the works in which she illustrates the defect of society analogues to the role of females and males. As a feminist writer, reflects the problems of women in patriarchal societies by referring to the conflicts between women and men. She criticizes the prejudice of the male-dominated society against women and underlines the necessity to eliminate the oppression imposed upon the female and to change the perspective of society towards women. Widely known as a feminist postmodern writer dealing with the issues related to women and their position in society, Fay Weldon, herself, experiences the misery and the suffering many women have been faced with due to the oppression of the male-dominated world. Being a single mother, she has to cope with financial problems and the hardships of life, as a result of which she begins to write about the problems of women. Therefore, her biography is compatible with her works in which she refers to the troubles of women and the oppression inflicted upon them. Moreover, being brought up in a house full of women, she finds the opportunity to witness the unfair situations happening to women.

Keywords: Fay Weldon, Praxis, Postmodernism, Feminism, Gender Problem, Weekend.

Praxis. In her one of the most box office-hit novels *Praxis*, Weldon explores the unexplored about the female identity and the struggles of women with society. The protagonist, Praxis, and the other female characters, portray the sufferings of women under the control of the male-dominated society. Thus, the importance freedom and equality in the lives of women is stressed through the experiences of Praxis and her relationship with the patriarchal society. The aim of this article is to emphasize how Weldon questions the secondary position of women and how she encourages women to challenge repression and restrictions exercised by the patriarchal society through her female characters in her novel.

The fat woman's joke. In this short novel the main character Esther Wells goes on a diet and the scales fall from her eyes. Depriving themselves of fatty foods, both husband and wife have new perspectives on each other, and the process is one of slow destruction of their marriage. Esther tells in flashback, from the depths of her basement apartment in Earls Court, the history of her marital disaster - in between her consumption of chocolate cake, tinned fruit, sweet sherry and a host of other high-calorie goodies. This novel examines the role of Womanhood. The time is the mid-sixties when sex role stereotypes are being examined and rejected, and Fay Weldon's book reflects the passions, humor, and anger of an era when women's self-analysis entailed a good deal of disruption. This novel depicts the rage and outrage of that traumatic era. In 1967 marriage and gender roles were still more rigid, despite the free love culture of youth, and I guess Weldon's novel must have seemed more radical (this time through I realized it's unpleasant Alan who writes a "cold, cruel" novel in this story which he thought was rather "warm and funny", and that I think is about Weldon herself, who agreed with me that only

laughter can make one bear life). They'd not be hugely memorable either, but nearly everything in this short novel is still depressingly true, forty years after she has written this novel.

Weekend. The short story weekend narrates about Martha, a middle-aged woman who dedicates herself to her family totally. She has to abandon her job in favor of her family members happiness. Everything in her home is on her shoulders, as a housewife and tries to be a superwoman by managing all these responsibilities. However, in this work the importance of cherishing the value of feminine beings is overlooked by her husband who follows old-traditional gender-task customs and does not worry about his spouse's inner thoughts. The author skillfully proves the idea of equal rights is a must consider while making a family with someone. the reader feels sorry for the position of Martha inasmuch as she never has time to think about her own intuitions and dreams.

It seems Martha has never lived for herself, done anything as she knows and decided anything independently. Fay Weldon compares women's role in the past and now as there is a huge discrepancy between them. Suffice it to say, in her all abovementioned works Fay Weldon contributes to the development of the feminism whose effects are widely observed in the lives of females of most societies.

Conclusion. Throughout most of Western history, women were confined to the domestic sphere, while public life was reserved for men. In medieval Europe, women were denied the right to own property, to study, or to participate in public life. At the end of the 19th century in France, they were still compelled to cover their heads in public, and, in parts of Germany, a husband still had the right to sell his wife. Even as late as the early 20th century, women could neither vote nor hold elective office in Europe and in most of the United States (where several territories and states granted women's suffrage long before the federal government did so). Women were prevented from conducting business without a male representative, be it father, brother, husband, legal agent, or even son. Married women could not exercise control over their own children without the permission of their husbands. Moreover, women had little or no access to education and were barred from most professions. In some parts of the world, such restrictions on women continue today.

As most writers Fay Weldon's written works inspire the approvals of this stream and emotional contexts provide with clear illustrations of their desperate feelings.

References:

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